

ISic3481

I.Sicily inscription 3481

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

architrave

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Brikinniai

Place of origin (modern)

near Scordia

Provenance

sporadic find during study on the site of Monte San Basilio

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lentini, Museo Archeologico di
Lentini

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336182

1. Εὐμάρηι APN [— — —]

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645102

EDCS 70900812

PHI 336182

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1323

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 41 no.16 fig.93

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